

MODA
MOdelling DATA providing a description
for **Near-field Excited Semiconductor Structure**
simulated in project **MMAMA**

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION			
1	USER CASE	<i>A planar semiconductor structure should be excited by using a sharp metallic tip (5-100nm). The electromagnetic energy should be injected into the system by utilizing a long thin (0.5mm) metallic wire (several millimetres), i.e. by exciting a guiding mode along the wire within the frequency range from 2GHz to 100GHz.</i>	
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1	<i>Continuum Modelling of Materials: Electromagnetic Model (Maxwell Equations) – tightly coupled with Model 2</i>
		MODEL 2	<i>Continuum Modelling of Materials: Semiconductor Model (Continuity Equation, Energy Conservation Equation, Momentum Conservation Equation) - tightly coupled with Model 1</i>
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	<i>To be filled at the later stage of the project.</i>	
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	<i>Available implicit time domain commercial solvers (such as for example Comsol) have considerable difficulties with such large aspect ratio models, even if only full-Maxwell simulations are considered. This is the main argument for own solver development based on a Discontinuous Galerkin (DG) explicit time domain solver. Purely electromagnetic (without semiconductor modelling) DG 2-D and 3-D solver were already developed and available in our lab.</i>	
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	<i>The chosen user case is a typical arrangement relevant for microscopic analysis of semiconductor structures that are the main topic of the project. The focus of our initial simulation efforts is to accurately model the material. Therefore a relatively simple geometrical arrangement consisting a metallic wire, tip and a planar semiconductor is considered. This structure could be in the initial attempts also simulated as a 2-D axisymmetric case. At the later stage of the project 3-D structures will be also simulated and measured.</i> <i>Model 1 will be used to compute the electromagnetic field in the entire structure by solving Maxwell equations. This will be achieved by utilizing our existing vector DG-FEM time domain solver. Model 2 should numerically solve semiconductor equations (electric current continuity equation, energy conservation equation, and momentum conservation equation) for computing the interaction between the electromagnetic field (obtained in the Model 1) and the charge carriers of the semiconductor. Model 2 delivers the velocities and charge concentrations that are used to obtain the current density vectors. The current densities are transferred back to Model 1 in each time step for computing the E- and H-field.</i>	

Workflow

Microwave Microscopy for Advanced and Efficient Materials Analysis and Production - MMAMA

MODEL 1

Time domain DG-FEM Electromagnetic Analysis

1		ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	Compute the E- and H- field of the entire structure for a given current density at each time step delivered by Model 2.
1.2	MATERIAL	Metal of the wire and its tip; Semiconductor
1.3	GEOMETRY	Planar semiconductor (2mm x 2mm), coaxial metallic wire (L=mm, inner diameter r=0.5mm outer diameter R= 2.4 mm), and metallic tip (R=5-100nm).
1.4	TIME LAPSE	The chosen frequency range is 2-100GHz. Depending on the goal of simulation and its nonlinear character (non-linear semiconductor equations) several periods of the source signal are to be simulated.
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	The electrical boundary conditions are PEC on the bottom below the sample and absorbing boundaries for the rest.
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	To be written at the later stage of the project.

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.0	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum Modelling of Materials: Electromagnetics	
2.1	MODEL ENTITY	Finite volumes	
2.2	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	Maxwell equations (tightly coupled with Model 2)
		Physical quantities	Spatial coordinates, time, E-field, H-field, magnetic permeability, electric permittivity, J-field.
2.3	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	ϵ and μ are measured values and J is computed as an outcome of Model 2.
		Physical quantities/descriptors for each MR	J is obtained from the unit charge, the charge concentration and its velocity.
2.4	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE	$\vec{J}(t) = -qn(t)\vec{v}(t)$	

	CONDITIONS	
2.5	SIMULATED INPUT	<i>Simulated input is a guiding wave at the beginning of the metallic wire. The amplitude and the frequency of the wave is to be chosen by the user. In addition to this EM-excitation the current density obtained as an output of Model 2 (4.2) is also used here.</i>

3	SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	<i>Time domain vector DG-FEM solver.</i>	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	<i>Self-developed code "Virtual Electromagnetic Lab" available for all the members of our institute.</i>	
3.3	TIME STEP	<i>The time step is determined by the stability condition of DG-FEM and depends on the size and quality of the mesh used. It is computed for each generated mesh.</i>	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<i>The computational domain should be surrounded by an appropriate absorbing boundary condition (ABC).</i>	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy limit of the numerical integration • Stability limit for the given mesh • Size of the air box, i.e. the distance to the ABC 	

4	POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<i>The E-field and H-field vectors in each element of the mesh should be obtained from the computed vector FEM degrees of freedom of each element.</i>	
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<i>The well-known standard vector FEM approach based on hierarchical vector basis is applied. The obtained magnetic and electric field vectors are used as an input of Model 2.</i>	
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	<i>Here we rely on the available error estimations of the vector FEM approach.</i>	

MODEL 2

Time Domain DG-FEM Semiconductor Analysis

1		ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<i>Compute the carrier concentration and velocity at each time step for the given E- and H-fields delivered by Model 1 and for the given temperature T.</i>
1.2	MATERIAL	<i>Semiconductor</i>
1.3	GEOMETRY	<i>Planar semiconductor (2mm x 2mm)</i>
1.4	TIME LAPSE	<i>The chosen frequency range is 2-100GHz. Depending on the goal of simulation and its nonlinear character (non-linear semiconductor equations) several periods of the source signal are to be simulated.</i>
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<i>The boundary conditions of the problem are ambient temperature (23 deg Celsius) for all boundaries.</i>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	<i>To be written at the later stage of the project.</i>

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.0	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	<i>Continuum Modelling of Materials: Semiconductor modelling and simulation</i>	
2.1	MODEL ENTITY	<i>Finite volumes</i>	
2.2	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	<i>Current continuity, energy conservation and momentum conservation equations (tightly coupled with Model 1)</i>
		Physical quantities	<i>Spatial coordinates, time, carrier concentration, carrier velocity, carrier momentum density, temperature, E-field, H-field.</i>
2.3	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	<i>Carrier charge is well-known, semiconductor time constants are measured, electric permittivity and magnetic permeability of the semiconductors are well-known known.</i>

		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR
2.4	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	Electromagnetic force: $qn\vec{v} \cdot (\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B})$
2.5	SIMULATED INPUT	Simulated input is a guiding wave at the beginning of the metallic wire. The amplitude and the frequency of the wave is to be chosen by the user. <i>This excitation results in a distribution of the electromagnetic field (Method 1, 4.2) that is used as an input into this model.</i>

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Time domain vector DG-FEM solver.
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Self-developed code "Virtual Electromagnetic Lab" available for all the members of our institute.
3.3	TIME STEP	The time step is determined by the stability condition of DG-FEM and depends on the size and quality of the mesh used. It is computed for each generated mesh.
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	The computational domain should be surrounded by an appropriate boundary condition permitting no escape of the charge carriers.
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accuracy limit of the numerical integration Stability limit for the given mesh

4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	The J-field vectors in each element of the mesh should be obtained from the computed charge concentration and velocity of each element.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	The well-known standard FEM approach based on hierarchical scalar and vector basis is applied. <i>The obtained result (charge carriers densities and their velocities) are used to obtain the current density and this vector field is transferred to Model 1 (as written in 2.5).</i>

4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	<i>Here we rely on the available error estimations of the vector FEM approach.</i>
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